

Design and generation of adapted route instructions for navigation of wheelchair users

Extended abstract of the COSIT 2024 doctoral mentorship program

Sanaz Azimi ✉🏠

Laval University, Quebec City, Canada

Introduction- Mobility is fundamental for the social participation of people with mobility disabilities (PWMD) using wheelchairs. Indeed, wheelchair users confront diverse social and physical obstacles in their daily activities. According to the Disability Creation Process model, mobility is an important life habit and depends significantly on the interactions between personal and environmental factors. Despite many research studies on the interaction of PWMD with the environment, there is still limited knowledge of these interactions. Better understanding the aforementioned interactions would help to design and develop more adapted assistive navigation technologies that can help to improve and facilitate the mobility and navigation of these people in urban environments. For instance, there is a gap between the standard turn-by-turn routing guidance provided by these technologies compared to the route instructions that a wheelchair user would need for navigation that might include information on accessibility, landmarks, traffic lights, crossing streets, intersections, etc.

Objective- The main objective of this research is to design and develop adaptive route instructions for wheelchair users compatible with their profile, and specific needs. This will help to better guide them during their navigation, decreasing their navigational error and cognitive effort, improving their performance, and positively influencing their social participation.

Method- This research work is part of a more global project called MobiliSIG (<https://mobilisig.fgg.ulaval.ca/>) which aims at designing and developing an adaptive navigation technology to help people with disabilities in their mobility and social participation. More specifically, this PhD project proposes to explore the navigational behavior of wheelchair users (e.g., their mental and visual behavior, their perception of the environment, their navigational errors, stops, confusion, etc.) through three complementary experiments. In the first field-based experiment, participants (i.e., wheelchair users) are invited to navigate on a predetermined route using Google Maps' route instructions while they are equipped with eye-tracking glasses. Their navigation is recorded by a camera and after arriving at the destination, they write their route descriptions and fill out a NASA-TLX questionnaire. The collected data is then used to identify the necessary information to define the components of adapted route instructions for their navigation. Subsequently, the proper formulation for route instructions is determined through an online survey to make route instructions more adapted to the users' profiles. After that, a route instructions generator tool is developed and integrated into the MobiliSIG application developed by our team. Finally, through a third field-based experiment, the adapted route instructions provided by MobiliSIG will be compared to the ones provided by the Google Maps application. In fact, a similar experiment to the first experiment will be performed and the performance (i.e., the number of navigational errors and stops and behavior) and cognitive effort of wheelchair users while using these two navigation services will be evaluated.

Results- This study helps to get a better insight into wheelchair users' interactions with the environment. Moreover, this research work contributes to the MobiliSIG project to provide adaptive route instructions for wheelchair users during navigation. We anticipate that the study will lead to more inclusive, efficient, and sustainable mobility of wheelchair users, enhance their social participation, and spatial learning, and upgrade their level of

2 Design and generation of adapted route instructions for navigation of wheelchair users

autonomy during navigation. Our project facilitates knowledge transfer to both experts and decision-makers in Quebec City, as well as a user community (ROP03) involved in the project, through close collaboration with them. Indeed, the findings of this project will be shared with and presented to the research project members and partners (Quebec City, PSVI, ROP03, and RTC organization) and the user community. In addition, the research results will be presented in several local, national, and international workshops, and conferences, and will be published in scientific journals as well.